

Cu⁺², Ni⁺² and Co⁺² Chelates of N-N'-Hexamethylene-*bis* (2:5:di-OH, Acetophenone/ Propiophenone/Benzophenone)

R. B. PATEL and J. K. VERMA

Govt. College, Daman

and

R. K. SEVAK

Arts, Science and Commerce College, Kholwad

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The Schiff bases N-N'-hexamethylene *bis*-(2:5:di-OH, acetophenone, propiophenone and benzophenone) are used to study their complex forming behaviour with the copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) ions. Elemental, molecular weight determination, conductivity, magnetic moments and electronic spectra were carried out to assign a square planar structure for copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) chelates.

The I.R. spectra shows the characteristic stretching vibrations of $\bar{\nu}$ (M-N) and $\bar{\nu}$ (M-O) below 500 cm⁻¹.

MUCH research work is being done now a days on metal chelates of Schiff bases^{1(a), (b)}. The present paper reports the study of the complex forming behaviour of the following Schiff bases with the ions copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II)

(i) N-N'-hexamethylene-*bis* (2 : 5 : di-OH-acetophenone)

(ii) N-N'-hexamethylene-*bis* (2 : 5 : di-OH-propiophenone)

(iii) N-N'-hexamethylene-*bis* (2 : 5 : di-OH-benzophenone)

Experimental

(a) *Preparation of Schiff bases* : The two moles of 2 : 5 : di-OH-acetophenone, 2 : 5 : di-OH-propiophenone and 2 : 5 : di-OH-benzophenone and one mole of hexamethylene diamine were refluxed in presence of absolute alcohol on water for thirty minutes. The yellow-brown precipitates of all the three Schiff bases formed were filtered and washed with 50% alcohol to remove unreacted ketones and finally they were dried and recrystallised from chloroform giving m.p. 189°, 130° and 169° respectively.

(b) *Preparation of Chelates* : The solid Schiff bases and buffered metal ions solutions of copper, nickel and cobalt were refluxed on water bath for two

hours. The cobalt(II) chelates of all the three Schiff bases were prepared by passing hydrogen gas during the preparation of these chelates. The reddish brown, yellowish brown and reddish black precipitates of copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) respectively formed were filtered and washed with water to remove excess of metal ions and then with 50% absolute alcohol to remove excess of Schiff bases. They were dried at room temperature. Because of less solubility in chloroform, benzene etc, they were not recrystallised. They are soluble only in D.M.F.

(c) *Analytical* : All the nine chelates were decomposed by perchloric acid and the estimation of metal ions were carried out by standard methods^{2,3}. The molecular weights determined cryscopically using Camphor as a solvent showed monomeric in nature⁴. The conductivity of all the chelates was determined in D.M.F. on 'Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge' proving their non-electrolytic nature⁵. The percentage of nitrogen in each case was estimated by Kjeldahl's method. The results of several such determinations are present in Table 1

The structure of all the three divalent metal chelates can be depicted as shown below :

Where M = Cu⁺², Ni⁺² and Co⁺² and R = -CH₃ → H₂SB₁
-C₂H₅ → H₂SB₂ -C₆H₅ → H₂SB₃

TABLE 1

No.	Name of chelates	Molecular formula	Mol. Weight		% of Metal		% of Nitrogen		Conductivity mhos cm ² /mole	Magnetic moment in B.M.	μ_{eff}	λ	ϵ
			Exp.	Found	Exp.	Found	Exp.	Found					
1.	CuSB ₁	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₂ - Cu	445.54	440	14.27	14.90	6.28	6.45	10	1.80		640 (108) 565 (230) 390 (5800)	
2.	CuSB ₂ ⁻	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ O ₄ N ₂ - Cu	473.54	490	13.43	12.89	5.91	5.78	10	1.84		630 (105) 570 (172) 390 (5600)	
3.	CuSB ₃ ⁻	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ O ₄ N ₂ - Cu	569.54	580	11.16	11.86	4.91	4.70	12	1.78		630 (102) 570 (170) 385 (5500)	
4.	NiSB ₁	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₂ - Ni	440.71	425	13.32	12.68	6.35	6.55	5	dia		590 (410) 515 (1050) 405 (4700)	
5.	NiSB ₂ ⁻	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ O ₄ N ₂ - Ni	468.71	480	12.52	13.10	5.97	5.80	10	dia		590 (420) 510 (1040) 410 (4700)	
6.	NiSB ₃	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ O ₄ N ₂ - Ni	564.71	540	10.40	10.89	4.96	4.72	5	dia		585 (410) 510 (1060) 410 (4800)	
7.	CoSB ₁ ⁺	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₂ - Co	440.94	435	13.38	13.98	6.35	6.18	10	1.89		660 (300) 510 (2500) 400 (7100)	
8.	CoSB ₂	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ O ₄ N ₂ - Co	468.94	490	12.57	11.82	5.97	5.76	15	1.92		670 (290) 510 (2500) 400 (6700)	
9.	CoSB ₃	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ O ₄ N ₂ - Co	564.94	550	10.45	10.90	4.96	4.82	10	1.93		670 (264) 500 (2880) 390 (7800)	

(d) *Magnetism* : The magnetic susceptibilities of all the chelates were determined on a Gouy balance at room temperature. The copper chelates show one unpaired electron as the magnetic moment $\mu_{eff} \sim 1.8$ B.M. on the basis of a square planar structure^{6,7}. The nickel chelates are found to be diamagnetic having zero unpaired electron on the basis of square planar structure^{6,7}. The cobalt chelates show one unpaired electron as the magnetic moment $\mu_{eff} \sim 1.9$ B.M. on the basis of square planar^{6,7} structure. The square planar cobalt(II) chelates show higher magnetic moment than the value ~ 1.7 B.M. expected on the basis of a spin only formula $\mu_{eff} = \sqrt{n(n+2)}$ B.M. for one unpaired electron due to orbital contribution which is due to mixing ²A_{2g} into ²A_{1g}. The value ~ 1.9 B.M. is consistent with a square planar^{6,7} structure.

640 nm ($\epsilon = 108$)
565 nm ($\epsilon = 230$)
390 nm ($\epsilon = 5800$)

These may be assigned on an idealised D_{4h} symmetry to the following transitions.

640 nm ²A_{1g} ← ²B_{1g}
565 nm ²Eg ← ²B_{1g}

The band at ~ 390 nm is quite intense and seems to be a charge transfer band. The nickel chelates show the following bands

590 nm ($\epsilon = 410$)
515 nm ($\epsilon = 1050$)
405 nm ($\epsilon = 4700$)

(e) *Electronic Spectra* : The electronic spectra of all the chelates were recorded on 'Spectronic-20'. The solvent used was chloroform. The copper chelates show the following bands

The first two bands ~ 590 nm and ~ 515 nm could be due to the electronic transitions ¹B_{1g} ← ¹A_{1g} and ¹Eg ← ¹A_{1g}.

The band at ~ 405 nm could be an intraligand band. The cobalt chelates show the following bands

660 nm ($\epsilon = 300$)
 510 nm ($\epsilon = 2500$)
 400 nm ($\epsilon = 7100$)

The first two bands at ~ 660 nm and ~ 510 nm could be due to the transitions

${}^2B_{1g} \leftarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and
 ${}^2E_g \leftarrow {}^2A_{1g}$

The band at ~ 400 nm could be a characteristic of charge transfer band.

(f) *I. R. Spectra*: The I. R. Spectra reveal the M-N and M-O stretching vibrations⁸ at ~ 480 and ~ 420 cm^{-1} respectively. The rest of the frequencies fit very well with the depicted structure.

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